

Yukawa Potential in Klein-Gordon Equation in Cosmological

Inertial Frame

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Abstract: We study Yukawa potential dependent about time in cosmological inertial frame. If we solve Klein-Gordon equation, we obtain Yukawa potential dependent about time in cosmological inertial frame.

Keywords: Yukawa potential; Klein-Gordon equation; Cosmological inertial frame

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1. INTRODUCTION

Our article's aim is that we make Yukawa potential theory in cosmological inertial frame.

At first, Robertson-Walker metric is

$$d\tau^2 = dt^2 - \frac{1}{c^2} \Omega^2(t) \left[\frac{dr^2}{1-kr^2} + r^2 d\Omega^2 \right] \tag{1}$$

According to Λ CDM model, our universe's k is zero. In this time, if t_0 is cosmological time[3],

$$k = 0, t = t_0 \gg \Delta t, \Delta t \text{ is period of matter's motion} \tag{2}$$

Hence, the proper time is in cosmological time,

$$\begin{aligned} d\tau^2 &= dt^2 - \frac{1}{c^2} \Omega^2(t_0) [dr^2 + r^2 d\Omega^2] \\ &= dt^2 - \frac{1}{c^2} \Omega^2(t_0) [dx^2 + dy^2 + dz^2] \\ &= dt^2 \left(1 - \frac{1}{c^2} \Omega^2(t_0) V^2 \right), \quad V^2 = \frac{dx^2 + dy^2 + dz^2}{dt^2} \end{aligned} \tag{3}$$

In this time,

$$d\bar{t} = dt, d\bar{x} = \Omega(t_0) dx, d\bar{y} = \Omega(t_0) dy, d\bar{z} = \Omega(t_0) dz \tag{4}$$

Cosmological special theory of relativity's coordinate transformations are

$$c\bar{t} = ct = \gamma \left(ct + \frac{v_0}{c} \Omega(t_0) \bar{x} \right) = \gamma \left(ct + \frac{v_0}{c} \Omega(t_0) x \right) \Omega(t_0)$$

$$\bar{x} = x \Omega(t_0) = \gamma \left(\bar{x} + v_0 \Omega(t_0) \bar{t} \right) = \gamma \left(\Omega(t_0) x + v_0 \Omega(t_0) t \right)$$

$$\begin{aligned} \bar{y} &= \Omega(t_0)y = \bar{y}' = \Omega(t_0)y', \\ \bar{z} &= \Omega(t_0)z = \bar{z}' = \Omega(t_0)z', \end{aligned} \quad , \quad \gamma = 1 / \sqrt{1 - \frac{V_0^2}{c^2}} \Omega^2(t_0) \tag{5}$$

2. YUKAWA POTENTIAL IN KLEIN-GORDON EQUATION IN COSMOLOGICAL INERTIAL FRAME

If we focus Klein-Gordon equation about Yukawa potential ϕ dependent about time,

$$\frac{m_\pi^2 c^2}{\hbar^2} \phi + \partial_\mu \partial^\mu \phi = \frac{m_\pi^2 c^2}{\hbar^2} \phi + \frac{1}{c^2} \frac{\partial^2}{\partial t^2} \phi - \nabla^2 \phi = 0 \tag{6}$$

In this time, Yukawa potential ϕ dependent about time is.

$$\phi = -\frac{g^2}{r} \exp\left(-\frac{m_\pi r c}{\hbar}\right) + A_0 \sin \omega t$$

Frequency $\omega = \frac{m_\pi c^2}{\hbar}$, m_π is meson's mass (7)

Eq(6)-Klein-Gordon equation is satisfied by Eq(7)-Yukawa potential dependent about time

In cosmological inertial frame, Klein-Gordon equation is[2]

$$-\Omega(t_0) \frac{1}{c^2} \frac{\partial^2 \phi'}{\partial t^2} + \frac{1}{\Omega(t_0)} \nabla^2 \phi' = \frac{m_\pi^2 c^2}{\hbar^2} \phi' \tag{8}$$

In this point, in cosmological inertial frame, space-time transformations in the type A of wave function and the other type B of the expanded distance are

Type A: $r \rightarrow r\sqrt{\Omega(t_0)}, t \rightarrow \frac{t}{\sqrt{\Omega(t_0)}}$, Type B: $r \rightarrow r\Omega(t_0), t \rightarrow t$ (9)

Space-time transformation of Yukawa potential ϕ' is depend on Type A

Hence, Yukawa potential ϕ' dependent about time is

$$\phi' = -\frac{g^2}{r\sqrt{\Omega(t_0)}} \exp\left[-\frac{m_\pi r\sqrt{\Omega(t_0)}c}{\hbar}\right] + A_0 \sin\left(\frac{\omega t}{\sqrt{\Omega(t_0)}}\right)$$

Frequency $\omega = \frac{m_\pi c^2}{\hbar}$, m_π is meson's mass (10)

Eq(8)-Klein-Gordon equation is satisfied by Eq(10)-the solution.

3. CONCLUSION

We solve Klein-Gordon equation in cosmological inertial frame. Hence, we found Yukawa potential dependent time in cosmological inertial frame.

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